

DAMAGE EFFECTS ON STRENGTH AND LIFE OF OXIDE/OXIDE CMC IN COMBUSTION ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this study, oxide/oxide ceramic matrix composite (CMC) test coupons were quasi-statically indented with a blunt conical indenter and then tested for tensile strength and fatigue life in a combustion environment. The CMC, designated as N720/A, constituted woven 0°/90° Nextel™720 fibers in alumina matrix. Two different sets of test coupons were indented to two different dent depths, with the deeper dent depth ~0.5 mm and the shallower dent depth ~0.2 mm. The tensile strength and fatigue life of the indented test coupons was determined in a combustion chamber where a combustion flame simultaneously impinged on the dent region as the mechanical testing progressed. The maximum temperature in the dent region was 1250 ± 50°C. The cyclic loads were applied at a frequency of 1 Hz and a stress ratio of 0.05 till either 90,000 cycles (25 hours) or failure. Optical and scanning electron microscopes were used to characterize damage in the test coupons that failed during mechanical testing. For test coupons that did not fail within 90,000 cycles, residual tensile strength was determined. Both the sets of damaged test coupons survived 90,000 cycles for a maximum applied stress less than 85% of the ultimate tensile strength. For test coupons that failed in tension and fatigue, the failures occurred right at the dent site. Optical and scanning electron microscope images of the failed test coupons showed damage modes of fiber fracture and matrix cracking at the dent site. For test coupons that did not fail, the residual strength and stiffness was not significantly different from that of virgin, dented test coupons. This showed that the combustion environment had minimum effect on material degradation during cyclic loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

The lightweight and high strength characteristics of Ceramic Matrix Composite (CMC) materials at elevated temperatures make them more suitable for use in aircraft gas turbine engines in comparison to the commonly used nickel based superalloys [1, 2]. Currently used nickel based superalloys in gas turbine engines are able to tolerate temperatures up to 1050°C, with occasional hotspots of 1200°C which is approximately 90% of the alloy melting point [2]. With increasing turbine operating temperatures, the propulsion efficiency of the gas turbine can be increased and CMCs are expected to be very useful in this regard. Of special interest in this regard are oxide/oxide CMCs, i.e. CMCs with oxide fibers and oxide matrix, as they provide good resistance to environmental oxidation [3-7].

Foreign object damage (FOD) due to impact from external sources like flying debris can damage the CMCs resulting in a significant loss in their strength [8-15]. Most CMCs on the verge of full penetration by impact show about 40-60% strength degradation [8-10, 15]. Kedir et al. [8] investigated damage both as a function of impact velocity and preload in tension and observed that the extent of damage and overall strength reduction depended both on the amount of preload as well as the impact velocity. The experimental investigations were performed at ambient temperature. Choi et al. [9] studied the FOD behavior of a SiC/SiC CMC at both ambient and elevated temperatures (obtained

using a furnace) and found out that the elevated temperature composite resistance to FOD was significantly less than their ambient counterparts. Yashiro et al. [12] investigated the characteristics of FOD in plain-woven SiC/SiC composites after thermally loading the CMCs up to temperatures of 1000°C using an infrared image furnace. It was observed that the impact resistance of the test coupons that were thermally loaded at 1000°C was significantly degraded from their virgin counterparts. One major drawback in the previous FOD studies is the lack of an environmental chamber that more realistically simulated the gas turbine engine combustion environment. This drawback has led to the development of a unique test facility where mechanical testing on CMC test coupons can be performed simultaneously in a combustion environment that closely simulates an aircraft gas turbine [16-22]. This unique test facility uses a High-Velocity Oxygen Fuel (HVOF) combustion gun that continually heats one side of the test coupons while mechanical loadings are applied simultaneously using a servohydraulic mechanical testing system. A number of tests have been successfully performed in this test facility on both oxide/oxide and carbide/carbide CMC systems under monotonic, cyclic and sustained loads [16-22].

The study presented in this paper utilizes this state-of-the art combustion test facility [16-22] to evaluate the strength and life of oxide/oxide CMC test coupons with pre-existing damage in combustion environment. Microscopy studies were performed to characterize damage at the fracture site for the test coupons that failed catastrophically during mechanical testing, and residual strength tests were performed on test coupons that did not fail. The findings of this study will help influence future damage tolerance decisions when these CMCs are used in actual aircraft gas turbine engines.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The CMC material used for this research, designated as N720/A, was manufactured by COI Ceramics of San Diego, CA and consisted of woven layers of continuous Nextel™ 720 fibers in Alumina (Al_2O_3) matrix. The Nextel™ 720 fiber, manufactured by 'The 3M Company', is a metastable mullite with a chemical composition (by weight) of 85% Al_2O_3 and 15% SiO_2 . A single panel of N720/A consisted of 12 plies of eight harness satin weave (8HSW) fabrics with 0°/90° fiber orientation. The woven fabrics were infiltrated with the matrix precursor of alumina by a sol-gel process, followed by a vacuum bagging procedure under low pressure (< 0.7 MPa) and low temperature ($< 180^\circ\text{C}$). This was followed by a pressureless sinter technique at 1150°C which was stopped when the composite reached the desired density of approximately 2.78 g/cm³. The final product was a plate with a nominal thickness of 2.8 mm, and a porosity and fiber volume fraction of 24% and 44%, respectively. The test coupons were machined using a water-jet cutter to length and width dimensions of 177.8 mm and 12 mm, respectively, from a 2.8 mm thick plate of N720/A.

The damage in the test coupons was created quasi-statically. The quasi-static indentation process is representative of FOD by low velocity impact and was preferred over an actual dynamic impact procedure since it allowed for better experimental control as well as repeatability in creating dents of similar size. It has been shown in the case of polymeric matrix composites that the nature and extent of damage is similar for both quasi-static indentation and low velocity impacts when the impact energy is low [23]. Figure 1 presents the set-up of the indentation procedure carried out using a servohydraulic mechanical testing system in ambient temperature. A blunt conical indenter was used for the indentation and details of the indenter geometry is presented schematically in Figure 2. The indentation was done in displacement control at a rate of 0.005 mm/s, with the test coupons resting (fully supported) on a rigid steel plate and gently clamped on two sides in order to prevent any movement during indentation. Fiberglass pads were used underneath the clamp tips to prevent any local crushing of the CMC test coupons at the clamp site. The test coupons were loaded to a pre-programmed peak machine displacement, determined prior by trial and error, that resulted in the desired dent depth. Once the peak displacement was reached, the test coupons were gradually unloaded. Two different sets of test coupons were indented to two different dent sizes, with the deeper dent depth measuring 0.5 ± 0.05 mm and the shallower dent depth measuring 0.2 ± 0.02 mm. The machine residual dent depth readings, evaluated using the load versus displacement plots, was

validated using a Taylor Hobson profilometer. The Zeiss Discovery V12 optical microscope was used to characterize the external damage in the dented region before they were tested mechanically in tension or fatigue.

Figure 1: Quasi-static indentation procedure set-up.

NOT TO SCALE

All dimensions are in millimeters.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of indenter geometry.

Monotonic tensile and fatigue tests were performed on the indented test coupons inside a combustion chamber. The chamber isolated the combustion jet flame noise. Figure 3 presents the experimental set-up inside the chamber, which primarily consists of a servohydraulic mechanical testing system and a combustion system. The combustion system consists of a HVOF combustion gun furnished with propane gas (C_3H_8), oxygen and compressed air where the compressed air acts as a coolant. Propane gas has similar combustion characteristics to JP-8 which is a commonly used combustion fuel in military aircraft [24-27]. The combustion flame simultaneously impinged on the dented region as the mechanical testing continued. As shown in Figure 3(b), only one side of the test coupon (dented side) was directly impinged by the combustion flame. The thermochemical data in Glassman [28] was used in preliminary calculations that defined the flame conditions for achieving the desired temperature of $1250 \pm 50^\circ C$ in the test coupon dent region. An exhaust system was incorporated that used high capacity fans and a duct to suppress heat build-up as well as guiding out potentially hazardous gases outside the building. This helped keep the test environment within all the pertinent safety codes. A Forward Looking Infrared (FLIR) thermal imaging camera (Figure 3(a)) was used to measure the temperature distribution on the front (flame side) of the test coupon. The temperature field along the test coupon length on the flame side was recorded every 10 minutes. Additional cooling was also provided using compressed air directly targeting the grip region (Figure 3(b)).

The CMC tensile strengths for the two different dent sizes were determined first in the combustion environment. The tensile tests were performed in load control at a rate of 25 N/s. Fatigue tests were then performed in the combustion environment where the maximum applied stress was a percentage of the post-indentation ultimate tensile strength (UTS) for a respective dent depth. This percentage ranged from 80% – 95%. The frequency and stress ratio for the fatigue tests were 1 Hz and 0.05, respectively. The fatigue tests were performed either to failure or to a run-out time of 90,000 cycles (25 hours), whichever came first. The 25 hour run-out time was chosen based on the assumption that some gas turbine engines run at their maximum operating condition for an accumulated total of approximately 30-60 hours in their lifetime [29].

Figure 3: Mechanical test set-up inside the combustion chamber with (a) the full view, and (b) a close-up view of flame impingement on the test coupon.

The test coupons that did not fail in 90,000 cycles were tested further in tension at room temperature for the evaluation of their residual strengths. The tests were performed in load control at a rate of 25 N/s at least 24 hours after the completion of the fatigue tests in order to ensure that the test coupons had sufficiently cooled down. The strength results were compared to the room temperature strength results of virgin test coupons with similar dent depths. The Zeiss Discovery V12 optical microscope and the Quanta 200 scanning electron microscope (SEM) were used to evaluate the fractured region of the test coupons that failed during mechanical testing. While the optical microscope was used to get an overall view of the fracture region, the SEM was used to get further details on the different damage modes.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 presents the load versus displacement plots for both the shallower (~0.2mm) and the deeper (~0.5mm) dent. It is evident from the plots that for similar peak loads, the measured residual displacement (assumed dent depth) is approximately the same. A Taylor Hobson profilometer was used to validate the residual displacement readings obtained using the machine data. Figure 5 presents a representative dent profile created using the profilometer for one of the dented test coupons. In every case the profilometer dent depth measurement was very close to the machine residual displacement. Dent depth summaries from both the profilometer and machine data are presented in Tables 1 and 2 for the shallower and deeper dents, respectively. The extremely good correspondence between the machine and the profilometer dent depth evaluations indicate machine compliance effects were at a minimum during testing. The designated use of each of the test coupons in the mechanical tests that followed are also stated in Table 1 and Table 2. The UTS values referenced in the tables is retrieved from the monotonic tensile tests. The test coupons for the deeper dent showed some visible back surface damage while those for the shallower dent did not.

Figure 4: Load-displacement plots for the quasi-static indentation procedure.

Figure 5: Representative Profilometer dent depth evaluation result.

Test Coupon No.	Machine Residual Dent, mm	Profilometer Dent, mm	Test Designation and Environment
1	0.18	0.18	Monotonic in Combustion
2	0.22	0.20	Fatigue in Combustion @ 95% UTS
3	0.22	0.21	Fatigue in Combustion @ 90% UTS
4	0.21	0.20	Fatigue in Combustion @ 85% UTS
5	0.21	0.20	Fatigue in Combustion @ 80% UTS
6	0.19	0.19	Monotonic in Ambient

Table 1: Summary of residual dent depths and test coupon designations for shallower dent depth.

Test Coupon No.	Machine Residual Dent, mm	Profilometer Dent, mm	Test Designation and Environment
1	0.50	0.55	Monotonic in Combustion
2	0.45	0.50	Fatigue in Combustion @ 95% UTS
3	0.47	0.49	Fatigue in Combustion @ 92% UTS
4	0.48	0.53	Fatigue in Combustion @ 90% UTS
5	0.47	0.48	Fatigue in Combustion @ 85% UTS
6	0.46	0.47	Monotonic in Ambient

Table 2: Summary of residual dent depths and test coupon designations for deeper dent depth.

In the evaluations that follow, the applied tensile and fatigue stresses are calculated based on the minimum cross-section area at the dent site. The minimum cross-section area, A , is calculated using the test coupon width (b), test coupon thickness (t), dent depth (d) and the indenter tip radius (R) as

$$A = bt - \frac{R^2}{2}(\theta - \sin\theta)$$

$$\text{and } \theta = 2\cos^{-1}\left(\frac{R-d}{R}\right) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) is developed assuming the dent cross-section at the maximum dent depth location is in the shape of a segment of a circle with a radius equivalent to that of the indenter tip.

Table 3 presents the combustion environment monotonic tensile test results for test coupons of both the dent sizes. The percentage reduction in strength is evaluated with reference to undamaged (without dent) test coupon strength which is retrieved from Mall et al. [18]. The percentage reduction in strength for the CMC with the shallower dent is 24% and for the CMC with the deeper dent is 65%. Although surviving catastrophic failure, most CMCs on the verge of full penetration by impact show about 40-60% reduction in their tensile strength [8-10, 15]. In this regard, a 65% reduction in strength for the CMC having the deeper dent is not surprising.

Damage Condition	Failure Stress, MPa	Failure Strain, %	% Reduction in Strength due to damage
Undamaged	167	0.41	-
Shallower dent (~0.2 mm)	127	0.30	24
Deeper dent (~0.5 mm)	58	0.12	65

Table 3: Results of monotonic tensile tests in combustion environment.

Figure 6 presents the normalized maximum applied stress versus no. of cycles plots. The normalized maximum applied stress is defined as the ratio of maximum applied stress to the UTS for the respective dent size. Figure 6 shows that the deeper dent test coupons survive 90,000 cycles when the maximum applied stress is equal to or less than 90% of the UTS, while the shallower dent test coupons survive 90,000 cycles when the maximum applied stress is equal to or less than 85% of the UTS. The results for the shallower and deeper dents are quite consistent with each other since they are within the experimental margin of error. A similar trend is noted for the undamaged test coupons where it is observed that they also survive 90,000 cycles in combustion environment when the maximum applied stress is equal to or less than 90% of the UTS [Figure 6, Ref. 18]. Figure 7 presents the normalized fatigue test results with respect to the undamaged CMC tensile strength. The plots in Figure 7 show that for a life of 90,000 cycles, the fatigue limit is approximately 30% and 65% of the undamaged CMC UTS for the deeper and shallower dents, respectively. As stated earlier, the undamaged CMCs survive 90,000 cycles when loaded at less than 90% of its UTS [18]. This shows that in the case of a pre-existing dent there is a significant drop in the fatigue limit of the CMC for a life of 90,000 cycles. This drop in the fatigue limit worsens with increasing dent size as shown by the results in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Normalized Maximum Applied Stress versus No. of Cycles plots for fatigue tests in combustion environment. Results for the undamaged test coupons were taken from Mall et al. [18].

Figure 7: Combustion environment fatigue test results normalized with respect to the undamaged CMC tensile strength. Results for the undamaged test coupons were taken from Mall et al. [18].

A summary of the residual strength test results and their comparison to their virgin counterparts is presented in Table 4. The percentage average residual strength is calculated with reference to virgin test coupon strength results. As noted in Table 4, the residual strength of the run-out test coupons for both the dent sizes is greater than 97% of the strength of their virgin counterparts. The strength reduction in the deeper dent test coupons is slightly more than the strength reduction in the shallower dent test coupons. The residual strength results again show that the influence of the combustion environment on the overall material degradation is negligible and any loss in strength is likely due to accumulated damage in the CMC as a result of the applied mechanical loads.

Damage Type	Virgin Test Coupon Strength, MPa	Run-out Test Coupon Strength, MPa		Average Residual Strength, %
		1	2	
Shallower	120	119	117	98.3
Deeper	73	71	70	97

Table 4: Residual strength test results.

The fractured region of the test coupons that failed under tensile and cyclic loads in the combustion environment were evaluated under both optical and scanning electron microscopes. Figures 8 and 9 present representative optical microscope and SEM images, respectively, of the fracture site. All the test coupons failed catastrophically right at the dent site. There was no observable difference in the failure mode as result of variation in the dent size (shallower versus deeper), loading type (monotonic versus cyclic) or environment (combustion versus non-combustion). For the latter, the non-combustion environment results were obtained from virgin test coupons tested in tension for the residual strength comparisons. In every case, as seen by the representative images in Figures 8, a brushy appearance showing considerable fiber pull-out and fiber fracture was observed at the fracture site. A close-up view of a bundle of fractured fibers is presented in Figure 9(a) which clearly resembles the brittle nature of the failure. Matrix cracks were also observed propagating away from the fiber-matrix interface as shown in Figure 9(b). The applied loads weakened the bonds between the fibers oriented in the loading direction and the matrix. This caused the fibers to slightly pull out of the matrix and cracks to form in the matrix especially in the vicinity of the fiber-matrix interface. The microscopy analysis showed no evidence of embrittlement in the CMC due to the combustion environment.

Figure 8: Optical microscopy images from the dent side of the fractured region.

Figure 9: SEM images showing the different damage modes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study involved tensile and cyclic testing of oxide/oxide CMCs in a combustion environment. The CMCs had pre-existing damage of two different sizes created quasi-statically using a blunt conical indenter. The reduction in the tensile strength of the CMCs as a result of the indentation damage was significant and proportional to the dent size, i.e. a 24% and 65% reduction in

tensile strength was noted for the shallower and the deeper dents, respectively. For both the dent sizes, the fatigue limit in the combustion environment is 85% of the post-indentation degraded tensile strength for a life of 90,000 cycles. However, when referenced from the UTS of the undamaged CMC, the fatigue limit for a life of 90,000 cycles is approximately 30% and 65% of the undamaged CMC UTS for the deeper and shallower dents, respectively. Thus, in the case of a pre-existing dent, there is a significant drop in the fatigue limit in the combustion environment and this drop worsens with increasing dent size. The test coupons which did not fail within 90,000 cycles showed residual strength that was not significantly different from that of their virgin counterparts. The residual strength evaluation results show that the influence of the combustion environment on the overall material degradation is negligible and any loss in strength is likely due to accumulated damage in the CMC as a result of the applied mechanical loads. Microscopy images of the failed test coupons showed damage modes of fiber fracture and matrix cracking at the dent site with no observable difference in the failure mode as result of variation in the dent size, loading or environment.

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